

STATE OF DEVELOPMENT OF GREEN ENERGY IN UZBEKISTAN

Abdikarimova Aynura Abay qizi

Tashkent State Technical University

Annotation. In this article, concepts related to the importance of the energy sector in the development of the country's economy and the specific characteristics of the development of green energy in Uzbekistan are presented.

Key words. Renewable energy sources, green energy, green technologies, wind energy, solar energy, hydropower, geothermal energy, wave energy.

The increase in human population on earth is increasing the demand for energy. Since the 2nd half of the 20th century, the need for electricity has been greatly increased.

In our country, major reforms are being carried out in the field of energy, which is considered one of the important sectors of the economy, ensuring environmental safety, environmental protection, rational use of natural resources. In particular, in the field of energy, comprehensive measures are being implemented in connection with the use of renewable energy sources and the introduction of energy-saving technologies, and certain results are being achieved.

In the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for the period of 2022-2026, to increase the share of renewable energy sources in Uzbekistan by more than 3 times in the next ten years through the wide introduction of "green" technologies and the implementation of projects in the field of "green" energy. important tasks have been defined. In performing these tasks, the role of educated and qualified personnel working in the field of renewable energy is of particular importance.

It affects the management activity in order to reduce the consumption of fuel energy resources while maintaining the production volume in the method of energy saving management. The increase in energy consumption, the decrease and increase in the cost of energy resources, the increase in dependence on imports, the pollution of the environment create the need to solve the problems of developing renewable energy sources while achieving energy efficiency and increasing the efficiency of using traditional energy resources. These factors motivated the rapid development of the energy sector.

Energy - a national economy that includes the generation of various types of energy, their transformation from one type to another, their transmission and delivery over a certain distance, their use in all areas, as well as the solution of theoretical and practical problems related to them the field of science and technology.

In order to increase energy capacity in the economy, it is necessary to rapidly develop the share of renewable energy sources.

Renewable energy is energy from natural sources that are regenerated faster than they are consumed. Sunlight and wind, for example, are such sources that are continuously replenished. Renewable energy sources are sufficient.

Renewable energy production is less harmful to the environment than energy from burning fossil fuels. That's why switching from fossil fuels, which currently account for the majority of emissions, to renewable energy is key to solving the climate crisis. Renewable energy is now cheaper in most countries and creates three times more jobs than fossil fuels

Of the renewable energy sources in Uzbekistan's energy balance, only hydropower of natural and artificial water flows currently makes up a significant share; its share is slightly more than 1 percent of all energy production. Other sources of renewable energy - solar, wind and biomass are used very little. In recent years, a number of projects on the use of solar and wind energy have been

implemented.

In recent years, large-scale work has been carried out to improve energy efficiency and expand the use of renewable energy sources in the economic and social sectors of our republic. In particular, a long-term strategy for the development of the oil and gas, electric power, coal, chemical, and construction industries aimed at ensuring stable economic growth in the Republic and increasing the level of well-being of the population, continuously satisfying the demand for fuel and energy resources is being implemented.

At the same time, the existing capacities of the fuel and energy network do not fully meet the growing demand for energy resources, and the energy consumption of our country's economy is much higher than the average of developed countries.

Currently, only ten percent of the total amount of electricity produced in the country is contributed by renewable energy sources, which are mainly produced by hydroelectric plants. Finally, it is necessary to fully utilize the potential of renewable energy sources such as solar and wind, which have great potential.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2022, the following is being implemented in accordance with the comprehensive program to further increase the energy efficiency of economic sectors and the social sphere, introduce energy-saving technologies and develop renewable energy sources:

- In order to further develop renewable energy sources, increase the share of consumption to 25% of the total volume of electricity production by 2030;
- Uninterrupted supply of energy resources to social objects in the regions;
- Installation of solar photoelectric plants and solar water heaters in private homes;
- Replacement of non-standard gas-burning devices of household consumers, as well as legal entities, with modern and energy-efficient gas-burning devices.

Besides,

- Encouraging the use of energy using equipment that generates energy from renewable sources by expanding the introduction of energy-saving technologies, giving tax and customs benefits;
- Rational use of non-renewable hydrocarbon resources, increasing the competitiveness of manufactured products, and on this basis, providing stable fuel and energy resources to economic sectors and the population;
- Transfer of efficient technologies in terms of renewable energy sources and energy consumption, production of equipment and components in this field at local enterprises;
- Ensuring the availability of guaranteed energy resources for the population, especially in remote rural areas, improving the quality of life of the population and increasing their well-being.

Solar energy - Uzbekistan is a sun-loving country, and taking into account its geographical location, the possibilities of using solar energy are huge. Solar energy is the most popular alternative to green energy. At the same time, most regions of our country have about 300 sunny days, from which 3000 hours of sunlight are received, and if this sunlight is converted into electricity, it is equal to several thousand trillion kilowatts. Thanks to this, it is possible to solve the growing energy problem in Uzbekistan.

Wind energy- Wind energy generated by windmills in open areas of the earth is also a good alternative to green energy. Wind energy is emerging as an unsuccessful alternative to renewable energy in Uzbekistan.

Hydropower - Water is an important natural resource and is also the main source of green energy, which includes tidal, wave and hydropower. In Uzbekistan, water energy is known as hydropower. In its report, the International Energy Agency called hydropower the "forgotten god of clean energy" and called on countries to include it as an energy source to achieve zero emissions. Taking

into account the displacement of dams and damage to the environment, if hydropower is used correctly, Uzbekistan can achieve the goal of zero carbon emissions by 2070.

Geothermal energy- Electricity produced by the heat of the Earth's interior is called geothermal energy.

Wave energy - Electricity is generated from waves that come into the oceans. It is infinite because it is free from contamination.

There are opportunities and motivations for wider use of the following technologies of renewable energy in the republic:

- Solar panels for water heating;
- Solar photovoltaic systems for electricity production;
- Microhydroelectric power plants for the production of electricity;
- Wind generators for electricity production;
- Biogas plants for electricity and heat production.

The development of green energy is becoming important not only in providing people with energy, but also in protecting the environment. Therefore, it is more important to support this industry in Uzbekistan.

For example, by 2026, it is planned to increase the capacity of solar and wind power plants to 8,000 MW, and as a result, it will be possible to save about 3 billion cubic meters of natural gas per year.

By 2030, it is planned to increase the capacity of solar power plants to at least 5,000 megawatts and wind power plants to 3,000 megawatts. It is also expected that the share of renewable sources in the production of electricity will exceed 30 percent.

In conclusion, green energy seems to be part of the world's future, and methods of using clean alternative energies to many of today's energy sources are being studied and put into practice. These easily replenished energy sources are not only beneficial for the environment, but also create jobs, improve the living

conditions of the population, and increase their sources of income. As long as the development continues, it will be beneficial for the economic development of the country. By developing a variety of green energy solutions, we can all create a completely sustainable future for energy supply without harming the world we live in. Green energy projects have been worked on for decades and experience has been gained.

REFERENCES:

1. Xashimova S. N., Abdikarimova A. A. BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNI TA'MINLASHDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA RAQAMLASHTIRISH.
2. Nig'matullayevna, X. S. (2024). QAYTA TIKLANUVCHAN ENERGIYA TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO'LLASH. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 39(1), 98-101.
3. N.T.Toshpo'latov, D.B. Qodirov. "Qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalari" (O'quv qo'llanma). Toshkent-2020.
4. A.V. Vaxabov, Sh.X.Xajibakiev. "Yashil iqtisodiyot" (Darslik) T.: "Universitet", 2020.
5. Hashimova S. N. GUARANTEED GREEN ECONOMY AND DEVELOPMENT //Экономика и социум. – 2022. – №. 4-1 (95). – С. 61-64.
6. Nigmatullayevna H. S. GREEN TAXONOMY: ESSENCE, APPLICATION AND EFFECTIVENESS //British Journal of Global Ecology and Sustainable Development. – 2024. – T. 24. – С. 84-87.